

Emergence of Human Resource Development in India: An Overview

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Abstract:

Human resource development is the integrated use of training of set of individuals of an organization, business sector or an economy, taking place within organization for the expansion of human capital through the development of both organization and individual to increase the effectiveness in performance and to initiate and manage the change. Human resource development is the integrated use of training, organization, and career development efforts to improve individual, group, and organizational effectiveness. HRD develops the key competencies that enable individuals in organizations to perform current and future jobs through planned learning activities. Groups within organizations use HRD to initiate and manage change. Also, HRD ensures a match between individual and organizational needs.

Meaning of Human Resource Development

The UNESCO states that Human resource development is the framework for helping employees to develop personal and organizational skills, knowledge and abilities through employees training, career development, performance management and development, coaching, mentoring, and organization development.

Soumya C says that HRD is a continuous and planned process helping the employees to acquire competencies such as, performance related capabilities, discover and exploit inner potential for future roles and strong professional wellbeing through performance planning, feedback, training, periodic review and creation of development.

Importance of Human Resource Development

Out of production resources human resource is a live and generating resource. It is required to be developed with the development of technology. For effective working it is needed to develop their competencies to improve overall effectiveness of the organisation. In the modern times, management has grown very complex and it has acquired new dimensions.

So to tackle the new challenges management has recognized the development of competency of people, coordination between people at different levels, minimizing production cost and improving productivity. The priority in personnel management has changed vastly. Now the tasks of framing rules, regulations and standing orders have been changed to promote the motivation generating factors and minimize the de-motivating factors for maximum capacity utilization.

According to Ragini P The importance of HRD can be judged by observing the following points

1. HRD and Restructuring of Organisations:

In past in most of the companies the organizational structure was very complicated. There were many hierarchy levels from top to bottom. The authority used to flow from boss to the person at lower levels in more time. It used to

reduce the effectiveness of the structure. Now due to development of managerial skills the focus is on flat organization. Management is interested to increase the span of control and make organization flat and wide by reducing the number of layers of subordinates. This has proved successful in present time. Further, the departments are formed not on the basis of functional specialization but on the basis of products and services. HRD has made these structural changes possible.

2. HRD and Global Competition:

Due to liberalization of world economies many multinational corporations have entered in different countries through export, licensing, consultancy, collaboration, joint venture, merger and acquisition and foreign direct investment. These have increased the level of competition in almost every country. It has become difficult to carry-out the business effectively. It has become a question of bread and butter for everybody in business. Now focus has been shifted towards development of competencies of employees. Organizations with competent and motivated manpower have proved themselves by giving better performance in quantity, quality for products and services. They are enjoying leader position in the market. Now importance of competent human resource has been realized to a great importance.

3. Technological Changes and HRD:

Due to development of science and technology industrialization started. Further improvement in these brought better machines and techniques. Due to globalization pressure the focus is on cost reduction, short production time, quality of products and services. In this situation unskilled person cannot deliver the goods as per expectations. They will be facing a lot of difficulties to work on the latest technology. Unless a person is trained the quality and quantity of performance cannot be improved even the organization may have machines and equipment of latest technology. With the latest

technologies people can work at distance or at home also.

4. HRD and Employee Empowerment:

In present global markets the MNCs are operating a number of foreign subsidiaries located in different countries. For example, a company based in USA, having its foreign subsidiaries in China, India, Brazil and Australia and involves a long distance. It has become very difficult to manage these units from its corporate office located in New York. It has been felt that such type of business can be managed if company is having motivated, talented and dedicated manpower. This is not possible to get such type of manpower. For this management has to put sincere efforts to procure, develop and motivate employees. This dream can be converted into reality through human resource development process only. After this only the company can vest its employees with more authority, increase their accountability. This leads to empowerment of employees only through HRD.

5. HRD and Outsourcing:

In present time it has become a need of the business to provide goods and services with lower cost. This compelled many companies to outsource their non-core activities. This helped to develop the concepts of tele-working and flexible timing. Now focus has been shifted to physically handicapped workers, women and workers from rural and backward areas.

They are forming a larger portion of working force and they can work at distance with flexible time. This contributes to cut down in house costs. Hence the need for training and development of such workers has been felt at micro and macro levels. Through proper training and development activities these workers can contribute to a good extent in cost reduction in operations.

6. Compensation to Top Management:

Top management compensation in US firms is fixed as per shareholder value. If the value of shares of the firms increases then the compensation packages of top management will be increased. This keeps the managers motivated and triggers them for good performance. To achieve good performance from employees and of organization as a whole the importance of higher level of skills and competencies is realized. Human resource development process contributes to achieve good performance from employees and of organization as a whole and helps to increase value of share of shareholders. This approach has not been adopted in India until now but in future it may be accepted.

7. HRD Job Satisfaction:

Organization where favorable climate for learning is created and facilities for training and development, career development and proper guidance are provided the employees take initiative

to learn more. This way they attempt to improve their skills, knowledge, aptitude and competencies. With higher degree of talents they are in position to perform their tasks without any difficulty. They get higher degree of job satisfaction. This provides solution to many labor problems and helps to maintain good industrial relations in that organization.

8. HRD and Employee Turnover:

Through HRD efforts the employees become competent and motivated. They work in a good organizational climate. They are satisfied at their work and facilities provided to them. They know their career path and try to achieve through sincere efforts. They would like to stay with the organization for a longer period. In the present competitive environment it is difficult to procure good employees but it is more difficult to retain them. Through HRD process the firms retaining their employees get competitive advantage by cutting labor costs. Further the firms get rid of hardly working employees by motivating through HRD process. The level of commitment and sense of responsibility in employees develop. This gives long-term positive impact on the business of the firm.

9. Bright Future of HRD Research:

To manage the business more effective and better than their competitors the management of the firms has realized that HRD process can help them a lot. Further to find out more and better HRD methods and intervention, research in HRD areas is needed. It is possible when the top level management is having HRD-oriented approach. From the analysis of the above mentioned point it has been accepted that the HRD process is very important. In future its importance will increase further. It is very difficult to ignore HRD function in a multinational corporation operating in different foreign subsidiaries.

Conclusion:

Human resource development is a systematic and planned activities designed by an organization to provide its members with the opportunities and facilities to learn necessary skills and develop competencies to perform the current jobs and prepare them for further jobs also. Human resource development process is facilitated by mechanisms or sub-systems like performance appraisal, training, organizational development, potential development, job rotation, welfare and reward.

People are helped to acquire new competencies through various systems continuously. This has been realized and accepted at macro, micro and individual levels. Under different universities and institutions degree and diploma courses in HRD

were introduced at graduation and post-graduation levels in different countries including India also.

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